

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ABOUT THE SURFACE ENERGY OF GRAPHENE

Yurov V.

*Candidate of phys.-mat. sciences, associate professor
TSK Vostok LLP, Karaganda, Kazakhstan*

Zhangozin K.

*Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
TSK Vostok LLP, Astana, Kazakhstan*

Kargin D.

*Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
NAO "L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University",
Astana, Kazakhstan*

Abstract

The "sessile drop" method for determining the surface energy of solids - γ is considered. For graphite and graphene, this method yielded average values of $\gamma_2 = 53.6 \pm 2.1$ and $\gamma_1 = 44.8 \pm 14.7$ mJ/m². The crystal cleavage method for graphite yielded an average value of $\gamma_2 = 3250$ mJ/m², which is 60 times higher than the γ_2 value obtained by the "sessile drop" method. Analysis of both methods showed that the "sessile drop" method for determining the surface energy of solids cannot be used without modification. We propose new methods for determining the surface energy of solids: 1) through the melting point of the solid; 2) through the size dependence of a physical property on the thickness of the deposited coating; 3) through the measured value of the contact potential difference. The following values were obtained for graphene: $\gamma_1 = 947.1$; $\gamma_1 = 960$ mJ/m², which is an order of magnitude higher than in the "sessile drop" method. The values of γ_1 should be multiplied by 3 and we obtain the values for graphite - $\gamma_2 = 2841$; $\gamma_2 = 2922$, $\gamma_2 = 2880$ mJ/m², which differs slightly from the crystal splitting method.

Keywords: graphite, graphene, surface energy, sessile drop method, crystal cleavage, solid.

Introduction

The use of surface phenomena in human production activities allows for the intensification of existing technological processes. Surface phenomena such as lubricating friction and wear, contact interactions, structural changes in composite materials, as well as electrical and electrochemical processes and phenomena on the surfaces of solids are important for technology. Knowledge of surface phenomena in living nature allows for conscious influence on biological processes in order to increase agricultural productivity, develop the microbiological industry, and expand the capabilities

of medicine and veterinary science. In biology, surface phenomena play an important role, primarily at the cellular and molecular levels of organization of living systems. Various biological membranes separate the cell from the external environment and ensure its microheterogeneity. Fundamental processes for life occur on cell membranes. Experimental determination of the surface tension of solids is complicated by the fact that their molecules (atoms) are deprived of the ability to move freely. An exception is the plastic flow of metals at temperatures close to the melting point. Graphene, discovered 20 years ago [1, 2], is an amazing material used in various fields of human activity (Fig. 1) [3-5].

Figure 1. Graphene and its applications [6].

Graphene is a two-dimensional allotropic modification of carbon formed by a layer of carbon atoms one atom thick ($R(I) = a = 0.246$ nm is the lattice constant)

in the sp^2 hybridization state. Carbon atoms in graphene layers are in a three-coordinated state, i.e. each of them forms covalent bonds with three neighbors. As

a result, a network of hexagons is formed, the vertices of which are carbon atoms, carbon-carbon bonds form the corresponding sides. The methods for obtaining graphene are quite diverse, a review of which is given in [2-6]. In [7-9], an original innovative technique for obtaining graphene with microcluster water in combination with ultrasound and an electric field is proposed.

The purpose of this article is to briefly review the determination of the surface energy (SE) of graphene and to propose our own theoretical and experimental method for determining the SE of graphene, which

plays an important role in all processes of human activity.

Determination of the surface energy of graphite and grapheme

Currently, more than twenty methods for determining SE (γ) are known. Many monographs, articles and patents are devoted to methods for determining the SE of solids (see the bibliography in [10, 11]). For graphene and graphite, the following SE methods are used: the "sessile drop" method (Fig. 2a) and the crystal cleavage (splitting) method (Fig. 2b).

Figure 2. Illustration of the sessile drop method with a liquid drop partially wetting a solid base (a); splitting crystals using a quartz wedge (b).

The sessile drop method uses Young's equation:

$$\cos \theta_C = (\gamma_{SG} - \gamma_{SL}) / \gamma_{LG}, \quad (1)$$

where γ_{SG} , γ_{SL} are the values of surface energies at the solid/vapor and solid/liquid interfaces, respectively; γ_{LG} is the value of surface energy at the liquid/vapor interface (surface tension energy).

In the method of I.V. Obreimov, cleavage (splitting) of crystals is carried out according to the formula:

$$\gamma = \frac{E \cdot h^2}{24(1 - \mu^2)} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \mu^2}, \quad (2)$$

where E is Young's modulus, μ is Poisson's ratio, h is the film thickness, u is the angle between the tangent to the curved contour of the split-off plate and the direction of movement of the developing crack mouth. In [12], using the sessile drop method, the SE of graphene and graphene oxide is 46.7 and 62.1 mJ/m², respectively, while natural graphite flakes demonstrate a

free surface energy of 54.8 mJ/m² at room temperature. In [13], it is shown that the PE of suspended monolayer graphene is zero, which indicates its superhydrophobicity. This follows from equation (1), where the contact angle θ of any liquid drop on a suspended graphene monolayer is 180°. This experimental result was confirmed theoretically using the molecular dynamics method. In [14] it is noted that one of the advantages of the wetting angle for measuring SE is that it is a widely used, relatively simple experiment that does not require expensive specialized equipment. In this work, it was found that the SE of the basal plane of graphite is 63±7 mJ/m², regardless of the size of the graphite flakes. The surface energy of the basal plane of graphene is 62±4 mJ/m², regardless of the size of the nanosheet. In the latest work [15], it was shown that the average SE values of graphene, graphene oxide and graphite are 44.8 ± 14.7, 47.9 ± 7.2 and 53.6 ± 2.1 mJ/m², respectively. Let us turn to the previous article of these authors and present their results in Table 1 [16].

Table 1.

Static contact angles and associated free surface energy.

Substrate	Liquid	$\theta \pm 1$	γ , mJ/m ²
Si	Water	64	66.75
Si/graphene	Water	92	42.49
Cu-clean	Water	68	60.42
Cu-clean	5.123M NaCl	87	44.76
Cu/graphene	Water	86	45.27
Cu/graphene	1.256M NaCl	77	51.06
Cu/graphene	2.022M NaCl	71	56.72
Cu/graphene	2.468M NaCl	80	48.85
Cu/graphene	2.775M NaCl	72	55.65
Cu/graphene	3.677M NaCl	75	52.74
Cu/graphene	5.173M NaCl	76	51.87

The most reliable version of the method for determining γ , based on the splitting of a crystal, was proposed in 1930 by I. V. Obreimov [17]. The idea of this

work is as follows. A plate is split off from a mica crystal along the cleavage plane, which, under the influence of the moment of forces acting against the surface forces, partially bends (Fig. 2b). This plate can be used

as a dynamometer measuring the splitting force. Recently, in work [18], a study was conducted by splitting mica in a way similar to Obreimov's approach, but using modern research methods. Adhesion energy: $W_a = 2\gamma = 0.81 \pm 0.38 \text{ J/m}^2$, in Obreimov [17] $W_a = 0.76 \text{ J/m}^2$, in works [19, 20] $W_a = 0.6 \pm 0.8 \text{ J/m}^2$, and in our theoretical work $W_a = 0.809 \text{ J/m}^2$ [21].

Obreimov's method was used for graphite in works [21-24], the analysis of which was carried out in work [25]. The SE of the prismatic face of graphite was equal to $\gamma_a = 1500\text{-}5000 \text{ mJ/m}^2$, the SE of the basal face of graphite was equal to $\gamma_c = 130\text{-}150 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. This is a significant difference between the values for graphite (see above). The reason why the sessile drop and crystal splitting methods give values with a difference of an order of magnitude is the following: firstly, the classical Young equation, obtained on the basis of the thermodynamic approach, does not work. Therefore, the equation of the contact angle requires a serious revision. And such a revision was made in the work [26]. The new equation of the contact angle is now called the Young-Verkholomov equation:

$$\cos \theta_C = (\gamma_R - \gamma_{SL}) / \gamma_{LG}, \quad (3)$$

where γ_A is the adhesion force at the solid/vapor interface; γ_{SL} , γ_{LG} are the surface tensions of the liquid

at the liquid/solid and liquid/vapor interfaces, respectively.

Secondly, the sessile drop method gives the value of the surface tension of the liquid on the solid, but not the surface energy of the same solid. This means that all works [12-16] based on the sessile drop method cannot give the value of the SE of a solid. This is due to the fact that according to Gibbs, it is necessary to distinguish between the surface energy and surface tension of solids; they coincide only for liquids. Today, the relationship between the value of the surface energy γ and the surface tension σ is determined by the Shuttleworth equation:

$$\gamma = \sigma + \Omega \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_T \quad (4)$$

Here Ω is the surface area of the solid; T is the temperature. This means that in Table 1 the value γ must be replaced by the value σ . This is confirmed by the fact that in Table 1 for copper Cu with water the value $\gamma = 60.42 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ was obtained. However, the exact measurement of the surface energy of copper by the "zero creep" method [27] is given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Surface energy of pure metals [27].

Metal	γ , mJ/m ²	Metal	γ , mJ/m ²	Metal	γ , mJ/m ²
Ag	1205	δ -Fe	1910	Si	2130
Au	1410	γ -Fe	2170	Sn	673
Al	1140	Ga	767	Ta	2480
Bi	504	Cd	820	Ti	1938
Cd	675	In	633	Tl	562
Co	2424	Mo	2630	V	1950
Cr	2090	Nb	2210	W	2690
Cu	1520	Ni	1940	Zn	868

From the comparison of Tables 1 and 2 it is evident that the sessile drop method is not suitable for graphite and graphene. Obreimov's method is also not suitable for graphene, since there is one monatomic plane, and therefore there is nothing to split.

Our methods for determining the surface energy of graphene

In [28] it is shown that the SE of a bulk crystal (graphite) γ_2 with an accuracy of 3% is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (5)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of graphene ($T_m = 4510 \text{ K}$).

In the graphite nanolayer (graphene), the size effect must be taken into account and the SE of graphene becomes equal to γ_1 [29]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 (1 - R(I) / R(I) + h) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) shows that the SE is three times smaller than the SE of the main crystal. From equations (5) and (6) for graphene it follows that $\gamma_1(\text{Gr}) = 947.1 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. The SE of the prismatic face of graphite turned out to be $\gamma_a = 1500\text{-}5000 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. The average value is $\gamma_a = 3250 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ and $\gamma_a / \gamma_1(\text{Gr}) \approx 3$, i.e. 3 times smaller than graphite (the main crystal). This means that the

theoretical value of SE for graphene is $\gamma_1(\text{Gr}) = 947.1 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. The sessile drop method shows that the SE values of graphene are 44.8 ± 14.7 , which differs from our value by an order of magnitude.

In [30-32], we proposed new methods for determining SE. They were based on the size dependence of the deposited coating. The first method involves measuring SE by determining the dependence of microhardness on the thickness of the deposited coating. The second method involves measuring SE by the dependence of the electrical conductivity Ω of the coating on its thickness h . These formulas:

$$\mu = \mu_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{d}{h} \right), \quad \Omega = \Omega_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{d}{h} \right), \quad (7)$$

where μ is the microhardness of the deposited coating; μ_0 is the "thick" sample; h is the thickness of the deposited coating, Ω_0 is the electrical conductivity.

The parameter d is related to the SE σ by the formula:

$$d = \frac{2\gamma \cdot \nu}{RT}, \quad (8)$$

where γ is the SE of a massive sample (graphite); ν is the volume of one mole; R is the gas constant; T is

the temperature. In coordinates $\mu \sim 1/h$ (μ is the inverse thickness of the deposited coating) we obtain a straight line, the slope tangent of which determines d , and the

SE of the deposited coating (γ) is calculated using formula (8). Let us now consider the determination of the SE of graphene deposited on a quartz plate using the magnetron method. The results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Dependence of microhardness on the thickness (a) and inverse thickness (b) of the graphene coating on a quartz substrate.

In the coordinates $\mu/\mu_0 \sim 1/h$ the experimental curve is straightened in accordance with formula (7), giving a value of $h = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$. For graphene $v = 5.3 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ and from relation (8) for SE we obtained $\gamma(\text{Gr}) = 974 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$. This, in principle, agrees with the obtained value $\gamma(\text{Gr}) = 947.1 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$ within the experimental error. In order to determine the SE of solids, we have developed a device [33], the essence of which is as follows. The method for measuring the contact potential difference (CPD) developed by us has the following features: CPD is measured by an oscilloscope that records the voltage and frequency of the periodically changing CPD between the controlled sample and the measuring electrode of the IE sensor of the device;

shielding of the sensor elements and wires; amplification of the recorded CPD; preparation of the surfaces of the part and the sensor for measuring the CPD. As a recorder of the CPD we chose a portable digital oscilloscope Micsig TO1104 of the tablet type, having a sensitivity of measuring the electric voltage of 0.5 mV. The sensor connected to the oscilloscope was developed by the authors themselves. The main part of the design of the sensor of the device for measuring the CPD is an electronic circuit, which allows the IE of the sensor, which is in contact with the metal part, to operate in a self-oscillating mode. In addition, the sensor includes a signal preamplifier. The complex for measuring the CPD, developed by the authors, is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Complex for measuring contact potential difference [33]

The energy γ was calculated by the formula:

$$\gamma = 0.028 \cdot 10^{19} \cdot \frac{\varphi - U \cdot 1.6022 \cdot 10^{-19}}{S} \cdot \left(\frac{\hat{I} \hat{A}}{\hat{I}_1} \right)^{0.3358} + 0.083. \quad (9)$$

If we now compare the values of the quantities: $\gamma(\text{Gr}) = 974 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$; $\gamma(\text{Gr}) = 947.1 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$ and $\gamma(\text{Gr}) =$

960 mJ/m², then we can say that the sessile drop method is not suitable for determining the SE of graphene, and perhaps for other solids.

Conclusions

The first experimental determination of the SE of solids was started by Tamman almost 100 years ago (1927) and continues to this day (Fedorov, 2023). The "sessile drop" method does not require special expensive equipment and this method has yielded SE values close in value for graphene and graphite over the past 15 years, but for graphite this SE value differs by an order of magnitude from the crystal cleavage method. Analysis of these methods showed that, despite the simplicity of the "sessile drop" method, it cannot be used to determine the SE of solids. The article proposes new methods for determining the SE of solids.

Gratitude

This scientific article was published as part of grant funding for 2024-2026, IRN No. AR32488258 "Development of innovative technology for producing graphene by intercalating graphite with microcluster water and modifying HTSC ceramics with graphene" (the research is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan).

References

1. Novoselov K.S., Geim A.K., Morozov S.V., Jiang D., Zhang Y., Dubonos S.V., Grigorieva I.V., Firsov A.A. Electric field effect in atomically thin carbon films // *Science*, 2004, V. 306, № 5696. - P. 666-669.
2. Novoselov K.S. Graphene: materials of Flatland // *UFN*, 2011, Vol. 181, No. 12. - P. 1299-1311.
3. Baimova Yu.A., Mulyukov R.R. Graphene, nanotubes and other carbon nanostructures. - M.: Russian Academy of Sciences, 2018. - 212 p.
4. Zhang T. Graphene. From Theory to Applications. - Springer, 2022. - 142 p.
5. Gupta R.K. (Editor) 3D Graphene. Fundamentals, Synthesis and Emerging Applications. - Springer, 2023. - 441 p.
6. Garshev A.V. Monitoring the development and implementation of technologies for obtaining graphene, its derivatives, other 2D crystals and the production of products based on 2D crystals in the Russian Federation and the world. - M.: RF Report, 2019. - 396 p.
7. Zhangozin K.N., Zhanabergenov T.K., Kargin D.B. About a new method for producing powder graphene // *Bulletin of ENU named after. L. Gumileva*, 2021, vol. 136, No. 3. - P. 8-16.
8. Zhangozin K.N., New method for obtaining graphene by intercalation of graphite with microcluster water. - *Almaty: Darkhan*, 2023. - 102 p.
9. Yurov V.M., Zhangozin K.N., Zhanabergenov T.K., Kargin D.B. Surface phenomena in graphite and obtaining graphene from it // *Science News of Kazakhstan*, 2024, No. 1. - P. 11-23.
10. Shebzukhova I.G. Surface energy and tension of metallic crystals, kinetics of adsorption of components of binary systems. - *Dissertations of Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences. - Nalchik*. - 2013. - 370 p.
11. Fedorov V.T., Kokoev M.N. Surface energy in the processes of grinding solids // *Bulletin of Dagestan State Technical University. Technical sciences.* - 2023. - Vol. 50(3). - P. 181-189.
12. Wang S., Zhang Y., Abidi N., Cabrales L. Wettability and surface free energy of graphene films // *Langmuir: the ACS journal of surfaces and colloids.* - 2009. - Vol. 25 - No. 18 - P. 11078-11081.
13. Su R., Zhang X. Wettability and Surface Free Energy Analyses of Monolayer Graphene // *Journal of Thermal Science.* - 2018. - Vol. 27(5934). - P. 1-5.
14. Ferguson A. The Surface Energetics of Low Dimensional Nanomaterials. - A thesis presented for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. - Trinity College Dublin. - 2016. - 188 p.
15. Rohman N., Mohiuddin T., Al-Rugeishi M. Surface free energy of graphene-based coatings and its component elements // *Inorganic Chemistry Communications.* - 2023. - Vol. 153(4). - P. 10855-110855.
16. Al-Rugeishi M.S., Mohiuddin T., Al-Amri Kh., Rohman N. Graphene Surface Energy by Contact Angle Measurements // *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering.* - June 2022. - P. 1-6.
17. Obreimoff J.W. The splitting reight of mica // *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930. - V. A127. -P. 290-293.
18. Johnson M., Brodnik N.R., Ekeh T., Bhattacharya K. Obreimoff revisited: Controlled heterogeneous fracture through the splitting of mica // *Mechanics of Materials.* - 2019. - V. 136(01). 103088.
19. Wan K.-T., Aimard N., Lathabai S., Horn R.G., Lawn B.R. Interfacial energy states of moisture-exposed cracks in mica // *J. Mater. Res.* - 1990. - V. 5(1). - P. 172-182.
20. Wan K.-T., Smith D.T., Lawn B.R. Fracture and contact adhesion energies of mica-mica, silica-silica, and mica-silica interfaces in dry and moist atmospheres // *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* - 1992. - V. 75(3). - P. 667-676.
21. Yurov V., Zhangozin K. About the mechanism of mica splitting // *Sciences of Europe.* - 2024. - No. 133. - P. 97-104.
22. Nozhkina A.V., Kostikov V.I. Surface energy of diamond and graphite // *Rock-destroying and metalworking tool - equipment, technology of its manufacture and application.* - 2017. - Issue 20. - P. 161-167.
23. Turchaninov M.A. Crystallization mechanisms of liquid carbon obtained by melting graphite with a laser pulse in gas environments with a pressure of ~10 MPa. - *Dissertation of candidate of physical and mathematical sciences.* - Moscow. - 2010. - 128 p.
24. Jiang Q. and Chen Z.P. Thermodynamic phase stabilities of nanocarbon // *Carbon.* - 2006. - Vol. 44, iss. 1. - P. 79-83.
25. Senut V.T., Vityaz P.A., Parnitsky A.M. Thermodynamic analysis of the formation process of a nanostructured polycrystalline material based on nanodiamonds modified with non-diamond carbon (part 2) // *Mechanics of Machines, Mechanisms and Materials.* - 2023. - No. 4(65). - P. 76-84.
26. Verkholomov V.K. Physical Features of the New Equation (Equation Jung - Verkholomov) of Contact Angle. // *Materials of the XII international research and practice conference "Science, Technology and*

Higher Education". December 21-22. - 2016. - Westwood, Canada. - P. 97-110.

27. Khokonov H.B., Taova T.M., Alchagirov B.B. Surface energy and surface tension of metals and their binary alloys in the solid state // KBSU. - 2019. - Vol. IX. - No. 2. - P. 5-19.

28. Rekhviashvili S.Sh., Kishitkova E.V., Karmokova R.Yu. On the calculation of Tolman's constant // Letters to the Journal of Technical Physics. - 2007. - Vol. 33. - Issue 2. - P. 1-7.

29. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S. Study of primary nanocracks of atomically smooth metals // Letters to the Journal of Technical Physics. - 2023. - Vol. 49, - Issue 8. - P. 35-38.

30. Yurov V.M., Portnov V.S., Puzeeva M.P. Patent. 58155 Republic of Kazakhstan. Method for measuring surface tension and density of surface states of dielectrics. Published 15.12.2008, Bulletin No. 12.

31. Yurov V.M., Portnov V.S., Puzeeva M.P. Patent. 58158 Republic of Kazakhstan. Method for measuring surface tension of magnetic materials. Published 15.12.2008, Bulletin No. 12.

32. Yurov V.M., Guchenko S.A., Ibraev N.Kh. Patent. 66095 Republic of Kazakhstan. Method for measuring surface tension of deposited coatings. Published 11/15/2010, Bulletin No. 11.

33. Yurov V.M., Makeeva O.V., Oleshko V.S., Fedorov A.V. Development of a device for determining work electron output // Eurasian Physical Technical Journal, 2020, Vol. 17, No. 1(33). - P. 127-131.